

Understanding the Image in the Digital Culture: The Quest for an Interdisciplinary and Collaborative Education

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Abstract: SDR Sistemas de Representación, is a pedagogic work which has been developed over the last five years at the Escola Tècnica i Superior d'Arquitectura La Salle. We have created a pedagogic methodology which integrates contents and methods with information technology in an innovative manner. The interdisciplinary nature of the course fits in with the nature of the technology. Visual communication, graphic design, art theory and computation, merge in a new conceptual framework that overcomes disciplinary boundaries. Ad-hoc web-based learning environments have been designed and implemented especially for this course, to support interdisciplinary and participatory thinking. The course is structured into six themes, each one dealing with a System of Representation: TEXT, FIGURE, IMAGE, OBJECT, SPACE and LIGHT. In this paper, we will focus on the content and methods of the theme IMAGE.

Introduction

The course *SDR Sistemas de Representación* is offered in the second and third years of an architectural program. Its philosophy follows a tradition that can be traced back to the Bauhaus[1]. To invoke a pedagogic tradition, however, does not mean to reproduce it as it was. The world in which the Bauhaus teachers and students lived in was the machine world, the industrial society. Nowadays, we live in the media world, the information society. Our reality is no longer determined by mass-produced objects as by the ubiquitous images distributed by media networks (television, film, video, advertisement, Internet). As Debray has written, "Aujourd'hui, notre réel, c'est une médiavision du monde, dispositif qui dispose de nous, doté d'une force d'entraînement planétaire" (Debray 1992, p.389). Therefore, today we must teach students to understand a world which is mediated by image[2]. Photography and film were the advanced techniques that the most progressive teachers of the Bauhaus, like Moholy-Nagy, could use to make their students understand the industrial world they lived in. Nowadays, we have digital technology as tools to produce digital objects (texts, objects, images) and as media to support collaborative processes of thought.

The course *SDR Sistemas de Representación* participates of the multi/inter/transdisciplinary approach to knowledge which is becoming the hallmark of contemporary culture. Its inclusive nature is manifested in the content, methods and tools. As for the content, the course is made up of theory bits taken from different disciplines. This structure evokes the associative nature of the web, where relationships become more important than the items themselves. The methodology follows the constructivist approach, according to which content is created together by students and teachers, participating in a common process of knowledge construction. Individual and collaborative exercises are closely intertwined with the theoretical structure. Finally, with regard to the tools, the exercises are done combining 'traditional' media (sketches, physical models, photography and video) with computer programs (word and image processing, drawing and modeling, animation, and multimedia authoring tools). Collaborative work is carried out on web-based environments, especially developed for the course.

[1] "... the basis of the growing work of the Bauhaus can never be too broad. Its responsibility is to educate men and women to understand the world in which they live and to invent and create forms symbolizing that world. For this reason the educational field must be enlarged on all sides and extended into neighboring fields, so that the effects of new experiments may be studied" (Bayer et al. 1975, p. 29).

[2] "Yet Western man has had, so far, no education or equipment for meeting any of the new media on their own terms. Literate man is not only numb and vague in the presence of film or photo, but he intensifies his ineptness by a defensive arrogance and condescension to 'pop kulch' and 'mass entertainment'" (McLuhan 1994, p. 195).

SDR: NETWORKING. A Web-Based Learning Environment to Support Collaborative Education

The web-based environment SDR: NETWORKING has been created to promote the active participation of students in a process of knowledge building (Scardamalia & Bereiter 1993). We began to design the system in 1999, and it was first applied during the academic year 1999-00. Since then, it has been continuously enhanced and improved (see <http://www.salleurl.edu/sdr/info>). At the current stage of development, SDR: NETWORKING is made up of three interrelated environments:

- *Environment 1*. It describes the pedagogic goals and teaching methods of the course. A gallery shows the most relevant works produced in the current and past courses. A news section provides information about exhibitions and conferences at other institutions. It can be accessed by any Internet user (see <http://www.salleurl.edu/sdr>).

- *Environment 2*. It contains interfaces to continue the themes discussed in the class; tutorials (software used in the course); and course administration (schedules, news, grades). It can only be accessed by students (Tab. 1).

- *Environment 3*. It is the core of the collaborative system. It is composed of six distinct environments, suited to the theoretical and practical requirements of each one of the six themes that make up the course: TEXT, FIGURE, IMAGE, OBJECT, SPACE and LIGHT (Fig. 2-5).

In previous papers we have described the philosophy and methodology of the course SDR in a comprehensive manner (Madrazo 2003) and we have expounded some of the six themes that make up the course (Madrazo 2001, Madrazo 2002). In this paper, we will focus on the theme IMAGE.

SDR: Image

The fact that we live in a culture dominated by image has been many times acknowledged by contemporary writers. As Debray has argued, between 1960 and 1980, Western civilization began to move from a culture based on writing (logosphère) and the visible (graphosphère), to a culture based on visuality (vidéosphère) (Debray 1992). This culture demands new forms of thinking, particularly with images: "Penser l'image suppose en premier lieu qu'on ne confonde pas pensée et langage. Puisque l'image fait penser par d'autres moyens qu'une combinatoire de signes" (Debray 1992, p.47).

However, the alleged substitution of a 'traditional' textual culture by a 'new' visual culture, it has become a matter of debate. For some scholars, it is clear that we are witnessing the disappearing of a culture based on the transmission of knowledge throughout the written word. Others, however, claim that textual culture will not disappear under the overwhelming presence of the image; rather, a new balance between the two languages -visual and textual- must be found. In this debate, information technologies could contribute to achieve a synthesis of all languages. Barrett, for example contends that "Thought and language in a virtual environment seek a higher synthesis, a re-imagining of an idea in the context of its truth" (Barrett, in Barret & Redmond 1997, p. xvi).

To understand this emerging culture we need new theoretical frameworks which enable us to understand the richness of the visual experience. An emerging area of knowledge, known as Visual Studies, would then be the result of overcoming previous disciplinary boundaries that divided the study of the image according to technique (analogue, digital), art form (painting, cinema), or function (art, advertisement) (Mirzoeff 1999). As Rodowick contends, "Visual studies holds together as a discipline through a consensus based on recognizing commonalities among 'visual' media -painting, sculpture, photography, cinema, video and new media- and the critical theories that accompany them" (Rodowick 2001, p. 32). Not only disciplinary boundaries should be eliminated, but also the distinction between theory and practice must be questioned, particularly in regard to the new media, since as Bolter has written, "The gap between media theory and the cultural practices that surround new media forms has grown wide, perhaps so wide that theory can no longer effectively critique these new practices" (Bolter, in Hocks & Hendrick 2003, p.24).

In classical aesthetics, the artist would find in nature the models to imitate. With the advent of the modern art avant-gardes, singularly after the Futurists, the machines of the industrial world would become the new models, taking the role of the productions of nature. In our information society, the sources of artistic creation must be

sought in a more intangible, albeit equally real, world: the world of images massively produced with all kinds of ‘visual technology’[3] and globally distributed through the most diverse media (film, television, video, press, Internet). Today’s art and architecture students, must develop a cognitive and aesthetic competence which enables them to elicit from a mediated world the sources for their creations[4].

Theoretical Content: Theory Bits

In the theme IMAGE, of the course *SDR Sistemas de Representación*, lectures on image theory are interwoven with exercises of image perception and image creation which students carry out individually and collaboratively, on a web-based learning environment specifically created for this course. The theoretical content is structured as a network of theory bits, that is to say, of atoms of knowledge borrowed from different disciplines (Fig. 1).

The lectures introduce students to the image culture, in its technical, philosophical, aesthetic and cultural dimensions. The network of theory bits for this theme includes myth and religion (Narcissus, the Bible), philosophy (Plato and the distinction image/idea), history of photography (from the camera obscura to digital imaging), aesthetics (cross-breeding relationships between artistic forms, like painting and photography, film and digital media), and advertisement (image semiotics, photomontage). This inclusive approach, whose ultimate goal is to create a transdisciplinary discourse around the image, conforms to the spirit of the emerging area of Visual Studies.

Threads connecting theory bits are elaborated during the lectures. The goal is not so much to explain each issue in depth as to highlight possible connections between them. Through these lectures, students become aware of the critical issues that will be developed further in the exercises.

Figure 1: Theory bits and threads of the theme IMAGE.

[3] “By visual technology, I mean any form of apparatus designed either to be looked at or to enhance natural vision, from oil painting to television and the Internet” (Mirzoeff 1999, p. 3).

[4] The architect Rem Koolhaas, defines ‘images’ in these terms: “Images have become our true sex object, the object of our desire. The obscenity of our culture resides in the confusion of desire and its equivalent materialized in the image....It is the promiscuity and the ubiquity of images, the viral contamination of things by images, which are the fatal characteristics of our culture” (Koolhaas et al. 1997, p. 787).

This is a summary of the topics we touch upon along the different threads:

The mechanical production of images

Along this thread, we explain students the basic history of the development of photography, from the camera obscura to photography, ending with the digital image.

Photography as art form

Introducing the interrelation between painting and photography at the time of impressionism, following with the advent of photography as new art form, the discovery of photography by modern artists (e.g. Rodchenko, Moholy-Nagy) and finishing with contemporary artists who use digital techniques to enhance the expressiveness of photography (e.g. Wall, Ruff).

Photomontage

Beginning from the early composition of negatives (e.g. Robinson), to the mixing of pictorial and photographic techniques in modern art (e.g. Lissitzky, Moholy-Nagy), to the use of photomontage as instrument of political and social critique (e.g. Heartfield), to end with the digital image.

The culture of the image

Starting with the recognition that a photography is an 'image of concepts' (Flusser 1984), that mediates between the subject and the world; following with the interpretation of the photographic image (Barthes 1980) and its truth (Sontag 1990); to continue discussing the ubiquity of the image in contemporary culture (Debray 1992) and the consequences of replacing discursive thought by visual thinking (Sartori 1997).

The meaning of the image in architecture

This thread has two poles: 1. the influence of images in the conception of architecture (images inherited from tradition, mental images, and digital images) and 2. photographic representation of a building (adequateness between the essential properties of the architectural object and its photographic appearances).

Exercises

The link between theory and practice is a critical aspect of this course. The purpose of the theoretical digressions is to build up a network of critical issues. Then, students develop this network further through the exercises. These exercises, therefore, are not meant to be the application of a previously established theoretical body. As a matter of fact, they are an extension of the theoretical discourse.

Individual and collaborative exercises are carried out during six weeks, according to this sequence:

1. Perception of the image in the mediascape. First, we develop the perceptual mechanisms of the students towards the visual environment produced by the different media: television, advertisement, video, film, press, Internet. Each student selects two images from any source and explains their meaning with a short text. The images are submitted to the web-based environment NETWORKING: IMAGE (Fig. 2). This way, a digital library is collaboratively created, with the support of the technology. Images are explained and commented later in the classroom.

2. Perception of the image in the urbanscape. Secondly, we exercise the student's capacity to perceive the 'physical', as opposed to the 'mediated', visual environment through the photographic camera. Students are confronted with the task to discover visual meaning in the urban environment. Each student makes two photos and introduces them in the environment NETWORKING:IMAGE, where images are classified in nine categories: aerial city, underground city, city in motion, inner city, public space, private space, reference objects, monuments and infrastructures (Fig. 3). On the web environment, students have access to the images taken by their peers, organized by author or by category.

Figure 2: NETWORKING: IMAGE. A collaboratively created digital library with images taken from any media. Photo: Henri Cartier-Bresson.

Figure 3: NETWORKING: IMAGE. View per category of the library of images of the urban environment. Photo: Anna Serra, SDR 03/04.

3. *Grouping images.* Once the digital library with images taken from the media and from the urban environment has been completed, the next step is to organize images in groups. Each student selects a set of images and describes what they have in common, according to their own interpretation. This is performed on an interface especially designed for this task (Fig. 4). To create a group, icons are dragged to the hot area at the bottom. Then, what the images have in common is explained with a short text. With this exercise, students develop their skills to interpret images and to associate meanings to them. This prepares them for the final step of the exercise: to express a personal view of the city by means of a photomontage.

4. *Creating a photomontage.* The end goal in this sequence of tasks is to create a photomontage -using image processing tools- which convey a personal idea about the city. The photomontage is composed of images previously collected from the digital library (Fig. 5).

Figure 4: NETWORKING: IMAGE. Interface to group images.

Figure 5: NETWORKING: IMAGE. Photomontage. Image by Esteban Bofill, SDR 03/04.

This simple web-learning environment, designed in conjunction with the exercises, is something more than a pure repository of information. It opens up a new space for reflection –still connected though to the activities in the classroom- where students can develop their capacities to understand the meanings of images and communicate these to their peers, by means of textual and visual languages in a multimedia environment. This space, we might argue, could only exist with the support of the technology. Nevertheless, technological issues stay in the background; the most important being the dynamic of knowledge construction that the environment brings about.

Conclusions

With the course *SDR Sistemas de Representación* we have created a pedagogic framework which integrates interdisciplinary knowledge, collaborative thinking processes, and information and communication technologies in an innovative way. The theoretical structure, made up of theory bits, enables us to deal with the different dimensions of the image, in a multidisciplinary way. The web-based learning environments, which were especially conceived for the course, allow students to transform visual information into knowledge, in a collaborative manner. The intertwining of the web environment with the lectures in the classroom facilitates the group dynamics and adds new values to traditional education. In this context, the web environment becomes a new space for the creation and communication of ideas, which would not exist without the support of the technology.

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